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**DIAGNOSTIC ALGORITHM FOR OPTIMIZATION OF
ELECTROPHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF UNDERGROUND
METAL CONSTRUCTIONS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE
QUALITY CRITERION AND THE METHOD OF NEURAL
NETWORK**

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The underground metal structures UMS operate in specific conditions of the soil environment under the influence of cyclic mechanical loads. It is necessary to conduct a detailed analysis of metal structures using non-destructive testing, as their damage and destruction during operation can lead to dangerous consequences. An improved method of resource calculation UMS and characteristics of diagnostic information circulating in automated systems for monitoring the technical condition of underground metal structures, taking into account the information-measuring system and decision-making system. A method of constructing a cyber-physical system CPS for modeling the electro-physical parameters of the system's underground metal structure and external aggressive environment taking into account the cathodic protection system and the decision-making unit on the ranges of change of informative parameters is also proposed. The method is based on a diagnostic algorithm for optimizing the electro-physical parameters of underground metal structures, taking into account the quality criterion and the method of neural networks.

Introduction. Analysis and monitoring of the parameters of the technical condition of underground metal structures (UMS) are important because damage and destruction of structural elements during operation can lead to dangerous and/or catastrophic consequences. In the process of complex analysis of the current state of the system of metal structures, it is advisable to take into account the operating loads and parameters that characterize their interaction with the environment.

Complex systems of this type (UMS) with a large amount of damage should be analyzed using neural networks (NN) and take into account all factors to avoid errors in predicting operating conditions. The principle of using neural networks is the continuous and automatic control of defects and damage caused by adverse conditions during operation.

The relevance of system research UMS is due to two main factors. First, the system UMS should be considered as a complex system taking into account many energy and kinetic parameters. This approach is complex and problematic. Secondly, the system UMS and its components should be applied to the method NN, because the application of this method allows ensuring a given accuracy of solving optimization problems and increase the efficiency of the computational algorithm.

Simulation of processes in complex systems using neural networks. As a result of statistical data analysis [1] it was found that the most acceptable for most tasks for the selection of parameter sets and assessment of the technical condition of UMS are multilayer neural networks, trained by the backpropagation algorithm Levenberg - Marquardt error. To implement the appropriate sequences of training on artificial neural networks, it is recommended to use a specialized software application Neural Network Toolbox in Matlab. Training error when setting in the application Neural Network Toolbox should be selected 5%. It is recommended for each case of the selected sets of informative parameters to perform training of 5-7 networks of the same architecture. This number of networks allows avoiding cases of convergence of the training algorithm to the local minimum and the effect of "retraining". This procedure will be accompanied by memorizing the target values corresponding to the information resources, rather than establishing a relationship between them [2].

For most cases, the most acceptable is the classical architecture of a multilayer neural network [3] with inverse error propagation. The mathematical expression for calculating the set of initial values y_{nm} of the neural network is as follows [4]:

$$y_{nm} = f_3(LW_{3,2}f_2(LW_{2,1}f_1(LW_{1,1}p + b_1) + b_2) + b_3) \quad (1)$$

As a transformation function in the source layer, we recommend using the sigmoidal function logsig , and in all hidden layers - the tangential-sigmoidal tansig . The mathematical expression of the logsig function is as follows:

$$\text{logsig}(n) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-n}} \quad (2)$$

The mathematical expression of the tansig function:

$$\text{tansig}(n) = \frac{2}{1 + e^{-2n}} - 1 \quad (3)$$

The peculiarity of tansig is that for most programs the calculation of its value is faster than for the hyperbolic tangent, and the results differ very little. The choice of the logsig and tansig functions as conversion functions is due to the following considerations:

- these functions are nonlinear, and, consequently, their combination in the structure of the neural network will make it possible to approximate the nonlinear multiparameter dependencies of the target data on the informative parameters;

- logsig is recommended to be used in the source layer of the neural network because the values of all parameters are previously reduced to the range [0; 1], which corresponds to the range of values of this function. The tansig function should be used in the hidden layers of the network because it has a higher sensitivity to minor changes in the inputs of neurons compared to logsig .

After completing the training process, all neural networks for all possible combinations should be tested using pre-selected test data sets that were not used during training. The obtained results of calculation of values of target parameters are compared with reference taking into account absolute and relative error, and also the corresponding average value. Among the obtained results of the outputs of neural networks, we choose the smallest.

The set of informative parameters selected according to the above criteria can be considered optimal and acceptable. The graph analytical method helps to analyze the physical essence of the obtained model, which is contained in the structure of the neural network and allows to work with the most optimal set of informative parameters. It can help visually track and analyze all the relationships between target and informative parameters, and also helps to avoid errors in the construction of algorithms for calculating UMS using microprocessor tools.

Since the dimensions of the "model" sets of input parameters and the target parameters obtained by calculating the neural network are the same, it is possible to construct two- and three-dimensional dependences of the target parameter on one or two inputs. The data sets thus obtained can be used to tabulate the dependence of the output parameter on the selected set of informative parameters in order to program microprocessors and build the appropriate software.

Model of diagnostics of underground metal structures. The diagram of the process of diagnosing the underground metal structure was built taking into account the quality criteria in the program BPWin Process Modeller and made using the module IDEF0. The corresponding diagram of the model is presented in (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Monitoring system for underground metal structures.

The decomposition scheme of the model is presented in (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Decomposition model of monitoring of underground metal structures.

The block diagram of the new system and the corresponding monitoring technology for underground metal structures are presented in (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Block diagram of information monitoring for the system "underground metal structure - aggressive environment".

The block diagram in (Fig. 3.) contains five blocks, of which the first block is responsible for collecting information, blocks second and three, are responsible for processing and storing data. Blocks four and five are the main system for estimating the parameters of the neural network.

Conclusions. A quality criterion for the algorithm of information processing, which is based on a neural network, has been formed. The functional that characterizes the resource, ie the term of trouble-free operation of the metal structure, is formulated, and an optimization problem is formulated for it.

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